

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES
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ANNUAL REPORT TO FOUNDATIONS

July 1, 1980 - June 30, 1981

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Council on Library Resources, Inc.

THE YEAR 1980-1981

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

July 1, 1980 - June 30, 1981

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1. As of November 1980
 2. Mr. Coles was elected to succeed Mr. Kempner at the November 1980 annual meeting.
 3. Until January, 1980
 4. Until December, 1980
 5. Until August, 1980
 6. Until December, 1980
 7. As of January, 1981
 8. As of March, 1981
 9. As of March, 1981
 10. As of January, 1981

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

Last year's report characterized the year as "busy." This year's activity might well be termed "incredible." Eighty-two grants and contracts plus interns and fellows were active during fiscal 1981, including new awards of almost \$2,000,000. Additionally, well over half of the projects were new, rather than continuations. Activities under the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) and the new Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship program (PETREL) accounted for much of the funding activity. Assessing these quantitative dimensions of Council activity provides some token of what is required to describe the increasing activity and interests of the range of projects, a range that conveys both the continuing and the changing interests of the Council on Library Resources throughout its twenty-five year history.

Certain themes are readily identifiable. The Council, for example, has always had an interest in projects that contribute to the profession as a whole, such as its support for the publication of the American Library Association's American Library Laws, and the current research on leaders in American academic librarianship coordinated by Wayne Wiegand at the University of Kentucky. International programs, too, have always been an important concern. While Council financial commitment in this area has somewhat diminished relative to overall activity,

its interest in projects that further library and development throughout the world have remained a major focus since 1956.

Undoubtedly the most important current interests of the Council in terms of financial commitment are the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP), initiated in 1978 for a five-year period, and the new Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL) program. Both are the products of deliberate and long considered efforts to enlist support for national bibliographic services and for improved professional education and training. The two projects represent both continuity and change. CLR has supported efforts to improve bibliographic services since its inception. Its interests in professional improvement also date from many earlier projects. However, organizing unrelated efforts or small projects into specifically defined programs implies somewhat greater commitment to particular areas.

The focus on topics such as library management remains an important Council interest. Management, operations, services and collections are closely interwoven and all have received CLR attention in recent years. Continuing support of the Association of Research Libraries, Office of Management Studies (OMS) and efforts to aid smaller schools through projects such as that of the Associated Colleges of the Midwest provide individual libraries with the means to assess their own programs and improve their operations. All these areas, in addition, are

affected by the BSDP concentration upon forging and improving a national bibliographic record service, and the PETREL program's interest in recruiting and training students, and formulating programs to address management training and research needs. A re-assessment of the Council's management intern program in light of these new efforts is planned for the coming year so that program coherence will be assured.

In forging its past programs and new initiatives, the Council is fortunate to have been able to call upon a number of groups and individuals within and outside the profession. Their confidential advice and counsel is of the greatest assistance, not only in evaluating proposals and defining program priorities, but also in the increasing amount of task force and committee work required to deal with technical detail and issue definition.

Beyond the needs of program interests and assessment, the Council has been involved in a number of endeavors that promise to improve communication channels among libraries, institutions and scholars. An example was the meeting convened in April, 1981 by the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), and the American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities (AAAH), with funding provided by CLR. The meeting took as its starting point the recommendations of the National Enquiry into Scholarly Communication, and a proposal by James M. Banner, Jr., president of the AAAH, to improve communication between the library and the scholarly community. Scholars, librarians and

association officials who attended the meeting agreed on two actions. First, the group agreed that lack of faculty information about research library issues is a central difficulty in improving communication, and suggested the experimental distribution of Library Issues, a monthly newsletter produced by the editor of The Journal of Academic Librarianship, to faculty members at several campuses. The Council has funded this activity. A second recommendation was that library issues be brought to the attention of scholarly organizations, especially through participation by librarians in annual meetings, for the purpose of bringing such new developments as online systems to scholars' attention. Participants agreed to work with scholarly associations to implement these suggestions.

Another recent initiative in sharing library concerns with university administrators and representatives from the scholarly disciplines is a joint CLR-Association of American Universities (AAU) effort to examine major issues facing U.S. research libraries. In February, 1981, the two organizations sponsored a meeting of university officials, librarians, and foundation executives. The twelve participants discussed five key issues: bibliographic data bases and the problems of access to bibliographic information; resource sharing and the attendant problems of collecting, preserving and making collections available; preservation of deteriorating books and other

materials; technological applications for libraries; and professional education and training for research library positions.

Five task forces have been formed to address these issues. Each group is scheduled to meet several times during the coming year to study the issues and to produce a report proposing specific actions for the immediate future. Finally, a conference for library directors, university administrators, scholars, and others is planned to advance the work of the task forces.

Working more closely with scholars and institutional officials as well as the major academic organizations and associations is a theme that has not been an explicit and prominent Council concern. Yet it underlies nearly all CLR activity. Cooperation is a readily identified Council priority in every activity. Extending cooperation to a wider forum of interested individuals and groups, and working to alleviate library problems of the 1980's through their communication and discussion is a variation on this old theme that deserves explicit recognition. Future CLR activity will undoubtedly require the assistance of a wider constituency and better understanding of libraries' relations to institutions and the scholarly disciplines.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICES

Changes in bibliographic processes and services during the last twenty-five years have been numerous, and the pace of change, at least from the vantage point of the early 1980's, continues to accelerate. Yet as far back as 1956, the year of the Council's founding, libraries were aware of the need to meet the demands of the "information explosion" through exploiting new technology for library purposes. The feeling that libraries had assisted in bringing about the age of automation and mechanization, but had gained little from its innovations was one factor that promoted the establishment of CLR by the Ford Foundation. From the beginning, technological assistance for bibliographic services and bibliographic access were important program interests. The Council's first report expressed the need to concentrate on "the exploration of technological means to solve problems that confront libraries in their service to scholarship and research."¹

By 1970, major bibliographic obstacles remained, even though automation promised some degree of assistance for the future. A rather wistful note in the Council's fourteenth Annual Report hypothesized a different world in which "the United States might have a single library system wherein the optimum degree of

centralization would insure the optimum use of resources to provide the best possible services to library clientele." There would also be a "single national data base in machine-readable form encompassing all types of library materials." However, the report concluded, "The sums of money required for such a system are obviously not now available and, even if they were, a single system of the type described probably could not be built." At least, the report added, not at that time, given the political realities and the rudimentary organization of available data.²

Nevertheless, the report concluded that one option was available, and that option consisted of cooperation and the consequent elimination of duplicate efforts. What CLR hoped to do was fit together existing efforts and encourage new ones. The cornerstone of the system was to be national bibliographic control: preparing standardized records and making them available economically, in either machine-readable or manual form, to all libraries. With the development of a machine-readable cataloging system at the Library of Congress and the MEDLARS system at the National Library of Medicine and with the growth of efforts to create a national serials data base, movement toward the provision of national library services had clearly begun.

More than ten years ago, criteria for the hoped-for national data base were firmly established. They included--then and now--comprehensiveness, authority, accessibility, timeliness, standardization, all at reasonable costs.³ Much of the Council's

work since that time has consisted of requesting, suggesting, encouraging, catalyzing, organizing and funding projects that could, finally, serve as parts of such a system. CLR has supported developmental work for networks and consortia, assisted programs that involve individuals and groups in cooperative efforts to build machine-readable data bases, and provided grants for efforts to develop standards--both national and international--to facilitate the exchange of bibliographic data.

By the late 1970's, a number of these groups had established common developmental principles. Defining the efforts as a coordinated program leading toward a specific goal had become an essential operation to assure continued cooperation and to enlist new collaborative efforts.

THE BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

In 1978, CLR launched the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) in order to serve some of the required functions of coordination and cooperation among bibliographic efforts already under way, and to assure funding of new projects. Funded by seven major foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities, the BSDP's goals are to provide effective bibliographic services for all who need them; to improve bibliographic products; and to stabilize costs (in constant dollars) of many bibliographic processes in individual libraries.

Wherever possible, the program employs existing resources, a specification which implies the cooperation of a number of groups and individuals including the major producers of bibliographic records.

One major prediction of the 1970 Annual Report has not changed. It is still unlikely that a single national data base, located in a single place, will ever exist. Aggregating the currently existing major bibliographic data bases seems more likely, and the BSDP has directed efforts toward that goal. Working closely with the Library of Congress, OCLC, Inc., the Research Libraries Group, Inc.(RLG), and the Washington Library Network(WLN), those who participate in the activities assisted by BSDP funds seek to identify and carry out tasks that will result in improved access to bibliographic information. A seven-member Program Committee composed of individuals with lengthy experience in bibliographic matters advises the Council on the program, ongoing projects, and new initiatives.

Major concerns related to the quality and accessibility of records are library use of bibliographic data bases and the needs of user groups. Midway through its funded five-year program, the BSDP has begun to assess online user requirements and reactions, and to gain an understanding of the implications of new technology for both public and technical services operations in institutional settings.

During the past fiscal year, the BSDP made more grants than in any previous year, and undertook major new program initiatives. Thirty-eight grants and contracts were active; new grants and contracts totalled twenty-five. New grant funding of more than \$1,000,000 was awarded. Details of BSDP project activity to date have been summarized in the Bibliographic Service Development Program Report, 1978-1980. An assessment of expectations for future bibliographic developments is contained in the program document Bibliographic Targets for 1984.

STANDARDS AND GUIDES

A major requirement for bibliographic record sharing is a common understanding of the intellectual content of the records and agreement on their organization. Standards operate to assure bibliographic consistency among record producers, and to facilitate record communication, processing and storage. A number of BSDP activities support efforts to formulate national and international guidelines and standards.

In 1979, the BSDP formed a Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards, composed of technical experts from the major shared cataloging systems, research libraries, the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and the Council staff. The committee continues in its role of advising the Library of Congress on the interpretation of the Anglo-American Cataloging

Rules (AACR-2) and the impact of these decisions on shared cataloging activities. In addition, the group advises on creation of manuals that will guide the application of the rules to specialized categories of materials such as newspapers, maps, archives and rare books.

Also in the area of applications, a manual on cataloging machine-readable data files has been completed. Sue A. Dodd, data librarian at the Institute for Research in Social Science at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, received a CLR grant in 1979 to produce the manual: Cataloging Machine-Readable Data Files: An Interpretive Manual.

Holdings statements and institution identification codes are also the subject of recently commissioned papers. Standardizing such codes would provide more ready access to valuable location information for researchers and interlibrary loan librarians. In 1980 the Council awarded contracts from BSDP funds to Howard and Patricia Harris and to Richard Anable to produce papers on identification codes and holdings statements.

The Harrises' paper, titled "Requirements and Design Considerations for a Standard Means of Library Identification," was completed in the fall of 1980. The authors review current standards efforts in this area, and present recommendations for what might constitute an acceptable standard. They also evaluate a series of design alternatives for identification codes.

The purpose of Richard Anable's paper is to explore the problems associated with holdings statements, the part of a bibliographic record that indicates an institution's ownership of materials. The paper, titled "An Investigation of the Holdings Statement Requirements Within a Location System," addresses both location and local inventory control functions of holdings statements. Anable writes that due to the increasing need to share resources, standard means of identifying what is owned at a particular library, and what parts are owned, are closely associated in building an effective location system. He recommends that local inventory control of holdings be incorporated into any holdings system design.

A particularly important and difficult to resolve problem over the past few years has been the simultaneous cancellation of copies of a serial by several institutions within a single geographic area. In an attempt to develop a system for preserving the last copy of a title in a region, the Pittsburgh Regional Library Center proposed, and received CLR funding for, the development of a prototype system for standardizing serial cancellations. Utilizing the Pennsylvania Union List of Serials, the project covers both OCLC and non-OCLC libraries, and aims at developing a method of recording and communicating cancellations through active use of an online union list.

Related to the BSDP objectives is another area of standards activity which has long been supported from the Council's general funds. Since 1961, support has been provided for the work of the American National Standards Committee Z39 (ANSC Z39). The committee is part of the American National Standards Institute, a federation of technical, professional, and trade organizations and commercial firms, which acts as a national clearinghouse and coordinator for voluntary standards in this country. Committee Z39 bears responsibility for standards in the library and information sciences, and related publishing practices. This year, based upon the committee's progress toward a program of self-support, the Council terminated grant funding for Z39. However, it continues to support standards activity through the BSDP and through work with a variety of individuals and groups.

Networks. In order to provide bibliographic products and services to libraries and their users, a number of organizations have been established during the last ten to fifteen years. Prominent among these organizations are about two dozen regional networks. Encompassing particular geographic areas, the networks are of various types, and they owe their existence, financing and defined scope to different kinds of legal instruments. Many, such as those that broker OCLC services, have been established to provide systematic access to bibliographic data bases and associated services.

As part of its interest in network services and their role in the evolving nationwide bibliographic framework, CLR has discussed many aspects of network organization, financing, goals and objectives with representatives of multi-state networks and other individuals. In late 1980, the Council contracted with James E. Rush and Norman Stevens to report on issues relative to these discussions, as a means of focussing commentary on a range of relevant issues. Their report, titled "Issues Relative to the Roles of State and Multi-State Networks in the Evolving Nationwide Bibliographic Network," was completed recently. The authors visited or held conversations with all state and multi-state networks, and national library associations, institutions and individuals. The report incorporates many of their concerns as well as those of the authors.

Bibliographic Data Bases. Central to the BSDP program is its concern with improving the quality and quantity of available bibliographic information in machine-readable form.

The Online Computer Library Center (OCLC, Inc.), The Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG), and the Washington Library Network (WLN), together provide several thousand libraries with online access to millions of bibliographic records. As components of a national information system, their data bases are the major bibliographic resources which might be linked to each other and to the Library of Congress to constitute a national database. The Council, through the BSDP, has been exploring the issues surrounding the

linkage of data bases, and in September 1979, signed a contract with Battelle-Columbus Laboratories to investigate the feasibility and impacts of such linkages.

In the Battelle-Columbus study, over 250 public and academic libraries were invited to supply data reflecting their experiences with the services of the shared cataloging systems. Based upon the results of the survey, and the hit-rate studies that were used to calculate the benefits of linking for shared cataloging and interlibrary loan verification, as well as estimates of the benefits for reference searching, Battelle recommended that the Library of Congress, OCLC, Inc., the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN), and the Washington Library Network develop online links. The contract report, Linking the Bibliographic Utilities: Benefits and Costs was published in 1980, and the Council subsequently issued a discussion of the report.

An interactive computer model called BIBLINK was developed specifically for the linking study. Its use enabled Battelle to analyze three types of links: direct tape delivery, "native" mode, and "translation" mode. A "native" mode link would require library users to know the languages used by all of the linked systems. In the "translation" mode, the computers automatically translate one system language into another. With the help of another BSDP contract, Battelle augmented the model and prepared

a user guide so that the model can be used by persons who might wish to experiment with different assumptions and data.

The Council issued another contract to Battelle to provide both a one-day orientation on use of the BIBLINK model and a subsequent four-month period during which BIBLINK would be made available by Battelle on its computer for use by the trainees via remote terminals. Held in March, the orientation session was attended by 15 library school faculty members and representatives of networks and utilities.

Data Base Structure. In September 1979, CLR called a meeting of the shared cataloging services and the national libraries to discuss the need for a nationwide authority file service. An authority file acts as a dictionary, or thesaurus, for the bibliographic data bases it controls. Because it contains the authorized and alternate forms of personal and institutional names and subject terms used to gain access to the records, it ensures that all relevant items can be found under accepted, standardized terminology. The absence of such consistency among currently operating systems is considered a major obstacle to the effective exchange of bibliographic data in machine-readable form.

Representatives attending the 1979 meeting agreed that the establishment of a comprehensive name authority file was both technically possible and highly desirable. Subsequently, the

Council funded a proposal from the Research Libraries Group, Inc., and the Washington Library Network to engage in a two-year investigation of the technical capability required to support a link between their authority file systems. The Library of Congress joined in planning and coordinating the project. Designated as the Linked Authority Systems Project (LASP), the major objective of the activity is to establish requirements and develop specifications, and a schedule of tasks for the deployment of hardware and development of software required for a telecommunications system and the machine interchange of records. When the project is completed, each network will continue to operate its own authority control system, but will also be able to share authority records with other networks.

In order to achieve long-range goals of linking bibliographic networks to each other and to local libraries that are members of these networks, it is necessary to establish communication protocols to be used by all participants. CLR has granted funding to Northwestern University to develop a means of computer-to-computer interchange of information. This protocol development would include several kinds of interchanges: sending textual messages between systems, transmitting records from one system to another, and individual search and retrieval of records from the data base of one system in response to a query from another system.

The Library of Congress (LC) name authority file is considered the basis for the projected comprehensive authority file. LC staff participation in planning, and its major effort to convert more than 100,000 LC name authority records to machine-readable form are being supported by CLR. In addition, Council funding made it possible for a U.S. representative from LC to attend an International Standards Organization meeting on an international authority system.

Technical requirements for an authority system, however, form only a part of the BSDP effort to implement an authority file service for libraries. The content of the records--their accuracy, consistency, and coordination of requirements--also requires major attention. To assure quality control and encourage cooperation in this area, the Council has formed a Task Force on a Name Authority File Service, which includes the participants in the LASP project, and others. The nine-member group is working out the guidelines and requirements for the service. Activities thus far have consisted of specifying both general and technical requirements and proposing guidelines to ensure that the content and format of authority records meet established standards. The recommendations of the Task Force are detailed in the April, 1981 report, Requirements Statement for the Name Authority File Service. This document has been distributed to members of the library community for comments and suggestions.

Subject Access. While name authority file work is now at a fairly advanced stage, the questions that attend subject file access are still being explored. It is possible that a series of subject files, each designed to meet the unique needs of special user groups, will develop. An important requirement might be to "map" these files--to draw attention to equivalent terms within data bases.

In its exploration of these possibilities, the BSDP has funded several efforts. A small planning grant to the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute for work on a thesaurus of art and architecture terms, and another grant to the American Association of Law Libraries to identify future steps in the implementation of a national law network (LAWNET) contributed to furthering work on the subject access problem. In 1981, Dora Crouch, Pat Molholt and Toni Peterson completed Indexing in Art and Architecture: An Investigation. The authors identified eleven projects that may help provide a beginning for establishing a standard indexing vocabulary for the two fields.

With reference to the more generalized problem of subject access to materials in research libraries, the BSDP contracted with Carol Mandel and Judith Herschman to produce a paper evaluating subject access systems in relation to the needs of researchers and scholars. The paper, titled "Subject Access in the Online Catalog" discusses research on subject access as it

applies to the problems and prospects of providing online subject access.

An ongoing effort to help shared cataloging services identify growth trends within the MARC data base is scheduled to run from February 1980 through February 1982. Martha Williams at the University of Illinois Coordinated Science Laboratory is engaged in compiling statistics and determining trends and relationships in MARC records, including frequency distributions of records for LC classes and data base characteristics such as field lengths. This information is expected to be useful to those engaged in establishing computer capacities for network use.

Products and Services. The enormous amount of attention given the technical characteristics of online data bases is characteristic of both the field in general and the first efforts of the BSDP. However, participants have always realized that they are concerned with providing data that will serve as a building block for library services. The kinds of products and services that are required and the user groups that need them have been discussed extensively at BSDP meetings.

Many institutions now provide direct public access to a bibliographic data base through online public access terminals. OCLC and RLG last year sought and received funds from CLR for a joint study of the approaches to the problems and priorities involved in online patron access to bibliographic data bases.

Their report, Online Public Access to Library Bibliographic Data Bases was issued in September, 1980. The report identified four topics of highest priority for further research: analyses of user requirements and behavior, monitoring performance of existing public access systems, developing methods for cost management, and developing distributed computing and system linkages.

Based on the report, CLR made additional grants and contracts to six different groups to coordinate efforts on a project to evaluate online public access catalogs. J. Matthews & Associates, OCLC, the Research Libraries Group, the University of California, Division of Library Automation (DLA), the University of Toronto Library Automated System (UTLAS) and the Library of Congress are working together in a two-phase project.

The major objectives of the evaluation are to produce comparative data on existing systems and to provide information for use in guiding future online catalog development. Information about the requirements of those who use the catalogs, and information about the performance of existing catalogs relative to user expectations and requirements are the subject of the data collection effort. The first phase of the project, funded for \$67,000, is concerned with the development of data collection instruments and standard forms. Phase II will include further refinement of the instruments, data collection and analysis and preparation of preliminary and final reports. Funds for these efforts and for the later data analysis activity to be

conducted by DLA totals over \$400,000. A number of public, college and university libraries are cooperating in the data collection efforts.

ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES MICROFORM PROJECT

A BSDP grant of \$20,000 was awarded in March, 1981, to the Association of Research Libraries for a two-year project designed to improve bibliographic access to microform collections in American and Canadian libraries. The prospect of adding to the national bibliographic files a number of retrospective records for items included in microform projects but never cataloged separately fulfills a long-held desire to make these materials more readily available. A major concern is to assure that national standards are accepted and followed in this endeavor and to make the records available to all libraries that wish to use them. The project emphasizes building on existing resources, coordinating efforts between the library and publishing communities, and the shared bibliographic services, and where possible, facilitating cooperative projects planned or under way.

CONSER

The Conversion of Serials project (CONSER) is a cooperative file-building effort that has resulted in a national serials data base. The Council funded and managed CONSER during the mid-seventies, but OCLC has since assumed the management role. The project served to confirm a belief basic to the development of a nationwide bibliographic network: that data base quality can be maintained even if responsibility for supplying records is shared.

CLR retains an interest in CONSER support and involvement. In 1978, the Council gave a grant to the National Library of Canada (NLC) to allow that agency to publish in computer output microfiche (COM) authenticated records from the CONSER project. This development enabled non-OCLC members to have access to the records. NLC plans to issue annual supplements to the CONSER microfiche.

The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada serve as centers of responsibility for the verification of records contributed to the CONSER data base by the participants. Eighteen libraries participated in CONSER in 1980. Verification--certifying the completeness and correctness of bibliographic data input by participating libraries--has been slow, and until early 1980, only half the records in the file had been authenticated. In January 1980, OCLC produced a magnetic

tape copy of all records in the data base as of December 1979. About 250,000 titles in the data base thus became available to libraries.

CLR has provided some assistance for a project to catalog the extensive journal collections of the Boston Theological Institute, a consortium that includes nine libraries holding over 7,000 unique titles. Completed this year, the project relied upon CONSER machine-readable data for conversion of the union list of serials. The Lilly Endowment and Arthur Vining Davis Foundation also contributed to the project.

The Council has continued to support telecommunications costs for some of the CONSER participants, in addition to the foregoing activities.

CATALOGING IN PUBLICATION

Supplying bibliographical information within a publication is an idea that dates back more than a century. Interest in this concept has never abated; one example of an earlier effort is the 1958-59 Library of Congress "cataloging in source" project, which the Council supported. In 1971, the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities joined in awarding a substantial grant to the Library of Congress to support a Cataloging in Publication (CIP) program. To date, CIP data has been prepared for over 200,000 titles, and currently appears in approximately

65% of the books published in the U.S. CIP has developed from a small charter group of 27 trade publishers to more than 2,000 active participants. It has also spread to publishers in other countries.

In 1980, after nine years of activity, the Library of Congress requested, and the Council granted funding to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of the CIP program. During early 1981, about 2,400 U.S. libraries of all sizes and types were surveyed to determine the extent and type of their use of CIP data. About 80% reported using CIP data for some purpose-- acquisitions, cataloging, and public services. The Cataloging in Publication Division anticipates preparation of a final report this fall. Results will be used to improve and perhaps expand the service.⁴

OCLC NON-ROMAN ALPHABET AUTOMATION

In 1978, CLR joined with the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Carnegie Corporation to support developmental work at OCLC, Inc., to allow OCLC to develop a non-Roman alphabet capability for its online system. The grant also supports developments in offline processes in which non-Roman alphabets are used.

The original grant has been extended through June 30, 1982. The first phase of development focuses on the Cyrillic and Greek

alphabets. Arabic and Hebrew will be added at a later date. During 1980, OCLC personnel worked to define terminal specifications and prepare software documentation. A consultant's report on the impact of the non-Roman alphabet capability on libraries using OCLC was received, together with recommendations for OCLC implementation. OCLC is now considering ways of modifying the non-Roman handling procedures to accommodate to AACR-2 rules.

1. Council on Library Resources, Inc. Annual Report I:10.
2. Ibid., XIV:17-18.
3. Ibid., XIV:18-20.
4. Library of Congress Information Bulletin 40 (Aug 14, 1981)
p. 265-266.

LIBRARY OPERATIONS AND SERVICES

Central to any assessment of the current status of research libraries is an awareness of the increasingly varied array of library programs and services. Certainly the use of computerized circulation systems and online bibliographic searching, for example, are changing the way libraries operate and the services they are able to offer. Due to a fairly bleak financial outlook, the new environment is a paradox of opportunity and the inability to take advantage of what is available. Managing this kind of changing environment is in itself a complicated task that involves at the highest level the relationship between the library and its parent institution and the library and the subject disciplines. At lower levels, it implies a whole new approach to assisting users and training staff members.

For a number of years, the Council has supported work aimed at improving management practices in individual libraries and at evaluating services and collections. This year a Council grant supported an American Library Association project to assess online search services in academic and research libraries. The college library's role in undergraduate education has been another major Council interest, as demonstrated in the College Library Program. As mentioned in an earlier section of this report, expanding and enhancing communication between librarians and scholars is a recent initiative that promises to aid in

defining ways to improve library involvement in the instruction process and in assessing more effectively the unique requirements of academic disciplines.

RESEARCH LIBRARY ECONOMICS

Related to these interests in furthering communication of faculty awareness of library needs and resources, and in librarians' involvement in the instructional, budget and planning processes, is another new Council-supported endeavor. Early in 1981 funds were granted to the Association of Research Libraries in cooperation with the Research Libraries Group, Inc. to explore issues of research library economics and financing.

Several concerns prompted the ARL-RLG proposal: first, efforts to improve the financial management of research libraries have been handicapped by inadequate information on the costs of library operations and services; second, the relationship between library operations and the academic and financial structure of universities is poorly understood; finally, the economics of the system of scholarly communication, which transcends library and institutional entities, deserves increased consideration in light of current financial strictures.

As a first step, ARL and RLG plan a meeting of invited participants to discuss the issues and to provide guidance on assessing currently available library cost data and budgeting

systems, and options for utilizing available information in making decisions. The meeting, to be held in October, 1981, is expected to constitute the framework for a longer research effort.

ACADEMIC LIBRARY PROGRAM

From the earliest years, a major element of Council programming has been support for efforts to improve administrative practices in libraries. Long-range program efforts began in 1968 with a case study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries. With CLR assistance, a planning office was established at Columbia, and a library research and development unit at the Joint University Libraries (now the Vanderbilt University Library) in Nashville, Tennessee received CLR support. An important result of the early activity was the 1970 establishment of the Office of Management Studies (OMS) within the Association of Research Libraries. During its first decade, the OMS has proved to be a productive force for improving management and financial control practices as well as providing training and other support activities for both ARL member libraries and others.

The OMS programs and activities are grouped in four major categories. To facilitate and improve the exchange of ideas and materials among ARL member libraries and others, the office operates a clearinghouse called the Systems and Procedures

Exchange Center. The center surveys member libraries on their current practices and future plans for specific areas of library policy and operations such as public services, preservation, staff development, and AACR II implementation. Results of these surveys are then made available to subscribing libraries. During 1980, the center distributed 6,000 publications and had 257 subscribers for its kit/flyer series, which consists of topical arrangements of member libraries' documents. A second OMS activity involves developing supervisory and managerial skills of library staff members. Assuming that individual staff members are more effective within the organization after they have acquired relevant skills and knowledge, the office maintains an ongoing effort to identify training needs and to develop resources and programs to meet those needs.

Related to the activities of the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center and to general ongoing OMS activity is a modest research effort. Office investigations and design work generally relate to OMS program activities; however, small separately funded projects are operated and the unit contributes to study projects operated by other agencies. Most research focuses on managerial concerns that face academic and research libraries. To encourage librarians to investigate these concerns, the office has begun a collaborative research/writing project. Two participants in this project have recently published papers on the topics of internal library communication and compensation structures in ARL libraries.

Most OMS office resources are directed toward development of the Academic Library Program (ALP). Within this program, the OMS staff assists individual libraries with planning and problem solving through the assisted self-study method. This methodology was first used to address general management issues. However, the program now comprises eight major study areas ranging from the original Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP) to new program areas, for example, preservation and public services. Twenty-eight libraries participated in the ALP during 1980. Using office program manuals and with staff assistance, selected members of the library staff at each participating institution examine the demands and pressures of the current environment, assess the library's situation, and design recommendations for improvements in programs and activities.

In 1978, the Council provided a \$326,000 grant for the ALP from funds received by CLR from the Carnegie Corporation of New York. Parts of the program are also funded by the Lilly Endowment, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the National Endowment for the Humanities, as well as cost recovery from participants.

During 1979, a new ALP program began with the selection of 20 well-qualified librarians to undergo training to become consultants. The program provides an opportunity for individuals to develop skills in identifying and diagnosing

library problems, study theoretical and conceptual elements of library training and consultation, gain experience in consulting, and obtain an understanding of OMS self-study procedures and their application. In 1980, each of the first 20 participants worked with OMS staff in a practicum experience which involved OMS training activities and co-consulting with OMS staff members in the conduct of ALP studies. Early in 1981, a second class of 20 trainees was selected from 159 applicants and trained in an intensive two-week workshop in March, 1981.

COLLEGE LIBRARY PROGRAM

The College Library Program was established in 1969 by the Council on Library Resources and the National Endowment for the Humanities. By 1978, the program had awarded grants to 35 college and university libraries to aid their exploration of ways to enhance library participation in undergraduate education. At the close of fiscal 1978, CLR and NEH discontinued the program, but because previous grants were for three to five year periods, final recipients will not complete the grant period until 1982. Nine programs remained active at the end of the fiscal year.

Each institution has developed its own specific goals and objectives. Success has been mixed, but student and faculty interest in program activities and institutional willingness to assume program costs after grant funds have terminated imply generally positive evaluation of the results of the program.

Pacific University, completing the program in 1980, titled its activities "Maximum Instructional Effectiveness through Maximum Usage of Library Materials." The final report noted that the university had assumed support of the Study Skills Center established under the grant and that this support would enable the library to continue to make its resources and services a "significant part of the student's liberal arts education" so that "an appreciation and knowledge of library resources can be a lifelong part of the student's learning quest."

Even more successful has been the program developed at the University of Wisconsin-Parkside. In 1977/78 the university instituted a competency in library skills requirement to accompany its other competency requirements in reading, writing, and mathematics. Upon receiving the grant, the library established five project goals in support of the competency requirement. The goals included perfecting a library skills test, developing methods and materials for team teaching a research skills course, enhancing library-faculty relationships, and developing subject workbooks for bibliographic instruction in a number of disciplines.

The project evaluation report noted that progress toward all goals was impressive: "The NEH/CLR grant has helped Parkside expand, intensify and strengthen the bibliographic instruction program on three levels: orientation, basic library skills and course- integrated library instruction. It has contributed to

the establishment of a model type bibliographic instruction program--in a state-supported community-based commuter college library...Parkside's administration and staff have made a long term commitment to bibliographic instruction by establishing as its mission to be a teaching library. Short and long range planning is guided by this mission. The Library/Learning Center has been reorganized to support the concept of the teaching library through traditional and outreach services."

The institutions at which libraries are still engaged in grant activities are: Johnson C. Smith University (N.C.), University of Evansville (Ind.), Northwestern University (Ill.), St. Olaf College (Minn.), Ball State University (Ind.), DePauw University (Ind.), Franklin and Marshall College (Pa.), Lake Forest College (Ill.), and Tusculum College (Tenn.).

LIBRARY SERVICES

A basic premise of the College Library Program is an emphasis on integrating the library more closely into the curriculum, through librarian-faculty, and librarian-student interaction. In some instances the program has provided the impetus for continuing library-faculty professional involvement and has enabled librarians to enter the classroom for the first time. Programs of bibliographic instruction, constructed and implemented in a variety of ways, have been the principal means of promoting this cooperation. The Council has continued to

support additional efforts to facilitate instructional efforts that involve library-faculty collaboration. Through 1979 grants to Earlham College and the University of Wisconsin-Parkside, the Council supported workshops to bring together librarians, faculty and administrators to discuss mutual interests related to instructional activities. The support funds were used mainly for faculty participants' travel.

A second grant to Earlham in 1980 provided additional funds to help defray expenses for twenty-five faculty members attending the College's fifth Conference on Bibliographic Instruction, held in April, 1981. That both faculty and librarian participants find this attendance helpful is shown by comments received after the fourth conference. One faculty participant wrote that "I have many new ideas and am thoroughly convinced that librarians are valuable teaching assets." Another enthusiastically noted, "It was far superior to what I expected. I thought I'd find myself in a group narrowly committed to getting students to using the library. Instead I found a faculty (instructors and librarians together) committed to improving the quality of instruction, committed to enrich their students' experience."

Moving beyond bibliographic instruction into newer areas that appear to offer significant potential for expanding library services has also drawn Council interest this year. Online bibliographic searching is one of the most promising new service initiatives in many types of libraries. Introduction of this

service promises to advance library ability to use technology effectively in delivering information to users and to serve as a pilot experiment in introducing technologically sophisticated services.

The question of how online search services should be financed, particularly in publicly supported libraries, has been a matter of debate ever since their introduction. Many libraries find it necessary to charge user fees for the service and there is a considerable diversity of practices and procedures in the absence of established guidelines on managing data base search services. After studying the question, the American Library Association proposed a research plan to assess the methods used by libraries to cover costs of online services and the Council granted funding for the project.

Through the major database vendors, Bibliographic Retrieval Services, Lockheed, and the System Development Corporation, ALA has distributed questionnaires to libraries that use online search services. Both publicly supported libraries and libraries in noncommercial organizations and institutions are included, and results of the survey will be analyzed by the ALA Office for Research. The data is expected to be helpful in aiding libraries' decisions to introduce online services, encouraging improvement and expansion of existing services, and helping libraries plan other technological innovations in the services area.

PUBLIC AND STATE LIBRARIES

While the Council's primary focus is on academic and research libraries, it sometimes receives proposals that include other types of libraries as the subject for investigation or support. On occasion, the Council has funded these proposals because it feels that support of particular projects may contribute to broader goals for the profession as a whole. For example, in 1958, 1960, 1963, 1977 and 1980, funds were awarded to the Library of Congress to support the Assemblies of State Librarians. These meetings provide a channel of cooperation between state agencies and the Library of Congress that otherwise might not be available.

Another Council-supported project in this area is the 1980 grant to the Plainedge Public Library in Massapequa, New York, for a research study to learn more about motivating nonusers or infrequent users to increase their use of public libraries. Surveys of nonusers were conducted by a consultant, Dr. Ernest Dichter, a well-known authority in the field of motivational research. Study results currently are being evaluated by the library.

ARCHIVISTS' SELF STUDY

During 1980, the Society of American Archivists received CLR funding to implement a program to test procedures for institutional evaluation of archival agencies. In view of the fact that very little formal, standardized preparation for archival work exists, the Society has begun to formulate evaluative criteria based on activities and services of archives. Self-study plus an onsite visit by an experienced archivist are the basic components of the evaluation.

The SAA Task Force on Institutional Evaluation has to date formulated documentation for the self-study and review process and tested the procedures in six archival institutions. Final results are being received and evaluated before the formulation of the project report.

LIBRARY RESOURCES AND THEIR PRESERVATION

One of the oldest and best known interests of the Council on Library Resources has been its continuing activity in the area of preservation. The level of interest among members of the profession, however, has not always matched that of the Council. During prosperous years, when library budgets increased annually, thoughts of collection deterioration received only marginal attention from librarians. Even disastrous floods in some European and American libraries did no more than spark an interest in freeze-drying wet books. Whether books crumbled in safe stacks, burned, or drowned by accident, preservation ranked low on practitioners' priority lists---particularly in comparison with topics such as collection building.

In recent years there has been an increase in general interest in preservation. In part, this is due to the seemingly greater frequency of accidents to collections. However, far more of the attention focused on preservation concerns is a result of losses in library buying power. Financial constraints mean that most individual libraries can no longer afford to purchase a major portion of the output of even U.S. presses. Because resources are not always available locally, preserving scarce copies of required materials and assuring their availability has drawn more and more attention.

For over a century, American books have been produced on acidic paper. Both the shift to wood pulp and the use of alum and rosin in treating paper contributed to the acidic content and to the short life expectancy of books produced on such paper. According to a Library of Congress Statement on Paper Durability, books printed on acidic paper will deteriorate in only 25 to 50 years.¹ Filming, restoring, recording, replacing or discarding are the alternatives for non-durable library materials. All these procedures are costly, and while librarians have recently been interested in establishing preservation units in libraries and encouraging new efforts in training preservation specialists, they are beginning to realize that changing the quality of the book trade output is an essential accompaniment to costly preservation practices.

COMMITTEE ON PRODUCTION GUIDELINES FOR BOOK LONGEVITY

During a quarter century of research, the Council has supported a laboratory devoted to chemical research on paper deterioration and the means of preventing it, sponsored efforts to develop specifications for selecting paper and bindings, and provided assistance for numerous meetings, studies and other efforts to found a national effort for preservation. In 1979, with the assistance of the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLR established the Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity. The committee, composed of publishers and librarians, studied the book paper problem as a first step toward its goal of considering all aspects of book longevity. On February 26, 1981,

the group held an all-day meeting at the Library of Congress under the auspices of the Center for the Book. Following the meeting, members met to discuss and draft their Interim Report on Book Paper issued in April, 1981.

The report of the Committee has a dual purpose: to increase awareness of the problem and to establish guidelines to assure permanence and durability. It contains statements regarding the present status of acid-free paper manufacture and a set of guidelines for paper to be used in book production. The Committee urges publishers to use acid-free paper and to identify acid-free books with appropriate statements in each book. Librarians are asked to make publishers aware of their preservation needs.

During the next year, the committee will continue its work, addressing the topic of binding. However, its activities are not the only CLR-sponsored effort in the preservation area. Now in its second year, a grant to the University of Wyoming to assist production of Conservation Administration News is a modest additional CLR preservation support activity. The newsletter is edited by the university's library director.

COLLECTION DEVELOPMENT, COLLECTION MANAGEMENT

As with preservation, the recent interest in collection management springs primarily from austerity. Collection development or collection building characterized the 1970's, but

it seems likely that elements such as library response to institutional change, interdependence among libraries, and local evaluation and analysis of collections will be major trends in the 1980's.

In support of the emerging theory and methods of collection management, the Council awarded a modest sum to the American Library Association to conduct a pilot collection management and development institute, held in connection with the annual ALA meeting in July, 1981. The institute was designed to introduce academic collection development officers and acquisitions librarians to concepts and techniques in the area, with the hope of replicating the program in other regions. The planning and execution of the institute was carried out by the Resources and Technical Services Division, Resources Section, Collection Management and Development Committee.

Practical problems of collection development and management also require attention. With the reduction in funds for the Library of Congress field office in New Delhi, the South Asian acquisitions program, operated at minimal cost to those research institutions involved, was severely cut back in most libraries. In response to a request from the Association for Asian Studies, CLR provided funding for a workshop in March, 1981, to review alternative ways to maintain support for acquiring South Asian research materials.

ASSOCIATED COLLEGES OF THE MIDWEST

In August, 1980, Arthur Miller, Jr., of Lake Forest College submitted the final report on the library collection use study funded earlier that year by a Council grant. The objectives of the project were to provide inexpensive and easily implemented methods for gathering collection use data and to provide guidelines to assist in the analysis and use of the results. Three ACM libraries participated in the data gathering effort: Lake Forest, Knox and St. Olaf. A major result of the activity was the production of a manual for performing similar studies.

Following up on the project, the Council in early 1981 awarded a grant to the Association of Research Libraries to review and to test the study manual. OMS will add a section to the manual on methods of describing collections, and will test the manual in four member libraries of the Cooperative College Library Center. The purpose of this project is to strengthen the procedural aspects of the study methodology, and provide a tested, refined program of wide interest and utility for college libraries. An advisory committee composed of the directors of the participating libraries, faculty members from each school, and the director of the Cooperative College Library Center (an Atlanta-based cooperative processing unit for a group of historically black institutions), has been organized to assist the project.

RESOURCES, SURVEYS AND GUIDES

Some assistance for collection development aids and materials for librarians continued during fiscal 1981. Since 1975, CLR has supported publication of a regular column evaluating new serials in Choice magazine, a book selection guide for college and university libraries. In 1979, a grant was awarded to the University of Kentucky Research Foundation for the purpose of assisting the production of essays on prominent academic library leaders whose careers spanned the 1925-75 period. The essays are being published in the Journal of Academic Librarianship.

During 1980, Etta Arntzen and Robert Rainwater published Guide to the Literature of Art History. The book was prepared as an update and revision of Mary W. Chamberlain's Guide to Art Reference Books (Chicago, 1959). A 1971 CLR grant supported preparation of the work, which lists about 40% of the titles in the 1959 edition, but with extensive revision of annotations. The number of pre-1959 titles has been reduced in order to provide space to list books published during the sixties and seventies.

1. "Library of Congress Statement on Paper Durability." Press release, Library of Congress, May 15, 1981. 4p.

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING

Every aspect of library professional education--quality, quantity, content, and other matters--has been a topic of professional debate. Most recently, discussions have focused on the financial realities and technological opportunity that will be faced by research libraries during the 1980's. A major question is how forthcoming changes in library administration, operations, and relations with other libraries and with parent institutions can be addressed in professional education programs. There has been long-standing concern on two counts: first, that truly exceptional candidates are not entering the profession due in part to the minimal material rewards; and second, that graduating students have not been sufficiently prepared to assume research library positions.

In order to define educational and other professional requirements, current information on the status of the profession is essential. The Council has long been interested in assessing librarians' status, and for several years funded a series of surveys on the compensation structures of academic librarians. Results that confirmed the general impression that the profession does not reward its members highly suggested a need for special incentives to attract high quality candidates and to assist their professional development.

A CLR grant to the American Library Association's Office for Library Personnel Resources has resulted in more complete information on the composition of the library work force and the related salary structure. Published in mid-1981, the survey results were issued as The Racial, Ethnic and Sexual Composition of Library Staff in Academic and Public Libraries (Chicago, 1981). The report will be useful for affirmative action planning since it includes statistics on the overall composition of the library professional work force by race, ethnicity and sex. Separate data for academic and public libraries and for individuals in selected positions are included.

During the late sixties and throughout the seventies, CLR programs and grants included a series of efforts to recruit specialists into the library field, to provide librarians with the opportunity to pursue advanced educational programs, and to allow mid-career librarians to improve their competence through study projects. Two intern programs, one for health science library interns and one for general management interns, were developed in order to help prepare promising candidates already working in the profession for leadership positions in academic and research libraries. Similarly, a writing seminar provided participating professionals with the opportunity to improve their writing skills, exchange ideas, and review each others' work.

These efforts to provide programs not otherwise available to the profession were similar in that they focused upon individuals, and provided educational experiences within practical situations--through course work, intern arrangements, individual study or peer review. They provided assistance for many individual librarians and indirectly, to the profession, but no direct answer to the concerns regarding professional education that continued to engage librarians' interest. Several themes emerge from the ongoing discussion.

One major concern has been that individuals who possess the professional degree have not received the kind of academic training that is needed for many, if not most, research library positions. Much library school course work is generalized, and the curriculum has failed to respond to specialized or unique requirements. Consequently, new library school graduates require substantial on-the-job training and some instruction in basic technical skills. How many graduates have had previous library experience is not known; however, for those who have not, the first library position often requires a major learning period. In a practice-oriented profession, this poses considerable difficulty for both supervisors and recruits.

Related to the concern about the professional education provided by library school programs is the perceived need for more advanced study opportunities in specific fields. A focus on interdisciplinary study provides many librarians with an

additional master's degree and some acquaintance with the special subject matter of an area other than library science. Formal cooperation of library science schools with the management and business disciplines would provide prospective library managers with relevant course work in specialized areas plus library science courses. Some opportunity for practical experience for aspiring library management candidates is a related consideration.

A third interest that is often discussed is the need for library administrators to acquire new knowledge. Because the profession is practice-centered, a bifurcation of research and practice has occurred. Library school faculty, whose research activities are generally more numerous and intensive than those of practicing librarians, do not necessarily base their efforts on current interests of practitioners. Beginning a dialogue between these two groups would provide each group with insights into the other's concerns. Forging an intellectual community among faculty and individuals who have recently assumed management responsibilities is one possibility for furthering intraprofessional collaboration.

A fourth area of interest, and one that promises to attract increasing attention during the 1980's, is the relationship of research libraries to their institutions and to society. Seeking the best professional help in studying economic, technical, political, and intellectual questions, calling upon

those with expertise in specialized areas, and utilizing their skills, requires a focused effort. Such an effort would aid library professionals in two ways: first, in obtaining the results of current research and opinions on the relations between institutions and the society; and second, in exploring the frontiers of knowledge in this area.

Considering these interests, the Council proposed and the Board of Directors agreed at the May, 1980 meeting to an expansion of CLR activities in the area of professional education and training. Assisted by funding of \$650,000 from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and \$450,000 from the Carnegie Corporation, the Council has begun a program planned for an initial three-year period. An advisory committee has been established to assist project planning.

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR RESEARCH LIBRARIANSHIP

The name of the new program is the Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL) program. The first work of the Advisory Committee has been to establish priorities for the program, to work with library schools in their efforts to design appropriate projects and to inform the library community of the project grants. Early decisions to concentrate on education and training issues that affect research libraries and to work with library schools reveal a focus on

formal education programs, but with added emphasis on practical opportunities and programs for librarians at different career stages.

Three library schools--the University of Chicago, the University of Michigan, and the University of California at Los Angeles--have thus far been granted funds to carry out specific aspects of the PETREL program. The major portion of grant funds is designated for the support of students. This appears to be the best way to attract well-qualified, promising candidates. New proposals for the expansion of project activities continue to be reviewed by the committee.

Each of the three schools is in the process of implementing a program to address one of the major concerns about academic library professional education. The Graduate Library School at the University of Chicago, in cooperation with the Graduate School of Business, has established a special postgraduate program leading to a certificate of advanced study in library management. The course work includes interdisciplinary study in library science and management, a special seminar to continue throughout the period of study, and investigative internships at participating research libraries.

The School of Library Science at the University of Michigan will begin an active recruiting program designed to attract a

small number of highly qualified candidates to specialize in research librarianship. An extended academic program, additional course work in related disciplines, research library internships and placement assistance are included in the new basic professional education program.

The Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of California, Los Angeles, has assumed responsibility for two projects. The first, designated a "Senior Fellows Program" is designed to provide an opportunity for specialized training for individuals who have recently assumed major management posts. A six-week course emphasizing managerial skills for research librarians with periodic follow-up sessions during the year of the fellowship will be developed as a prototype for a continuing program.

A second UCLA project is for a conference designed to explore and describe the frontiers of research librarianship. The objective of the initial week-long conference is to relate research library development and operations to the economic, technological, political and intellectual factors that promise to dominate policy making for the next decade. UCLA has been given support to host the first of a series of such conferences, to be attended by librarians, university administrators and others who have specialized skills pertinent to the agenda.

As the year ends, the new efforts are well under way and both Chicago and Michigan have established advisory committees to assist their progress. The PETREL advisory committee continues discussion of a host of topics, including support for research on major issues relevant to research library management and operations. The theme of all activities is to provide distinctive opportunities for professional growth of exceptional research librarians, to develop improved capacities for professional education, and to establish and help carry out a research agenda pertinent to research library functions.

ACADEMIC LIBRARY MANAGMENT INTERN PROGRAM

An early indication of the Council's interest in professional education was the establishment of the Management Intern program eight years ago. The program is designed to assist in the development of management skills of potential candidates for administrative positions in research and academic libraries. Applicants must be librarians who are U.S. or Canadian citizens or who have permanent resident status in either country. Most successful applicants enter the program with five years' professional library experience, usually including some administrative responsibility.

Each intern spends an academic year working closely with the director and administrative staff of a major academic library. The programs for individual interns vary, but the essence of the program is to enable an intern to study how a director of a large

library system handles responsibilities and deals with an array of long and short-term problems and issues.

Chosen from a class of 67 applicants, the 1981-82 class of interns brings to 35 the total number of participants in the program. This year, for the first time, two interns are assigned to one institution, the University of California at Los Angeles. The two are expected to work together on many projects.

The following interns were chosen to work with directors of four academic libraries during the 1981-82 academic year:

Anne W. LeClerq, associate professor and head of the undergraduate library at the University of Tennessee, Knoxville, will work with Russell Shank, University of California at Los Angeles. Ms. LeClerq received a B.A. from Duke University and the M.L.S. from Emory University. A CLR fellow in 1974, Ms. LeClerq's contributions to the literature include articles on non-print media and its library applications.

Patricia McClung will also work at UCLA with Russell Shank. Her career includes service at the Harvard University library, and since 1975 she has been with the Alderman Library, University of Virginia, as North American Bibliographer. Her library science degree is from Simmons College.

James G. Neal, head of the collection management department at the University of Notre Dame, will intern with Stuart Forth, director of libraries at Pennsylvania State University. His degrees are a B.A. in Russian Studies from Rutgers, and an M.A. in history and an M.S. in library science from Columbia University. He has also earned a certificate in advanced librarianship from Columbia.

Virginia F. Toliver is coordinator of computer assisted retrieval services at the University of Southern Mississippi. She will work with Charles Churchwell, dean of library services at Washington University. Formerly acting director at Alcorn State University Library, Lorman, Mississippi, Ms. Toliver received her M.L.S. from the University of Illinois.

Karen Wittenborg will work next year with Jay Lucker, director of libraries at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Her current responsibilities are as social sciences bibliographer and reference librarian, Stanford University. Formerly at the State University of New York at Buffalo, Ms. Wittenborg held several positions at that university and later moved to Albany as reference librarian and social sciences bibliographer. Her M.L.S. is from SUNY, Buffalo.

As the year ended, the Council decided not to select a class of interns for the 1982-83 academic year. Instead, the program will be suspended for a year in order to allow evaluation of its

results and to assess future prospects in the context of PETREL projects. During the course of the review, the Council will request assistance from the librarians and hosts who have participated in the program, and from the PETREL advisory committee. Others will also be asked to contribute to the review, which is the first conducted since the beginning of the program.

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

The three-year contract with the National Library of Medicine that supported the Health Sciences Management Intern Program ended with the completion of the internships of the three librarians selected for the year 1980-81. However, the Council's interest in the special field of medical librarianship continues. Early in 1981, a PETREL project grant went to the Medical Library Association for support of a study group designated by MLA to investigate the organization's role in the educational process for health sciences librarianship.

Archives management is another another specialized field, one that has been the subject of Council attention primarily in connection with international projects. As a result of a Council grant this year, students in the graduate program of Archival and Historical Administration at Wright State University will receive practical experience by pursuing internships in national agencies or institutions. During the summer of 1981 students

interned at the Chicago Historical Society, and at the National Archives and Records Service, in Washington, D.C..

Formal faculty development programs are relatively new in many academic institutions. However, faculty no less than practicing librarians are affected by changes in course work stimulated by new technology. Helping library school faculty to acquire new skills was the intent of a grant to C. W. Post Center of Long Island University. At C.W. Post, the library school proposed to add course work in information sciences to the curriculum. However, only a few faculty members possessed the expertise to teach the course. With funding from CLR and the Exxon Education Foundation, faculty from the Rutgers Graduate School of Library and Information Studies conducted course work in basic information science for five C. W. Post faculty members during the year 1980-81.

NEW ENGLAND ACADEMIC LIBRARIANS' WRITING SEMINAR

The final result of the Seminar appeared in 1980 with the publication by Scarecrow Press of Essays from the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar. Seminar members had published other work in library journals during the 1977-78 period of grant activity.

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMS

The vision of a national library system composed of a federation of compatible networks is of comparatively recent date. It follows that ideas for an international library system made up of national and multinational networks, employing a variety of computerized and manual techniques are an even more current conception. Only in recent years has such a development seemed possible. Yet, over time, librarians have tried to effect international agreements on recorded and cataloged information so that there would be few impediments to exchange. Through international organizations, they have sought to improve technical knowledge and to assist library development throughout the world. Their cooperative efforts in automation and bibliographic control are another part of a general effort to standardize the manner of exchanging bibliographic records and to prevent or diminish efforts to obstruct the free flow of bibliographic information.

CLR has always conceived its role as seeking solutions to library problems without regard to geographic limits. In practice, this has meant maintaining an interest and providing financial assistance for activities designed to further library cooperation, bibliographic development and communication among libraries all over the globe. The Council has worked with organizations, institutions, and individuals to facilitate basic

work and communication necessary for further development. Major funding for these efforts during the last two years has come from the Exxon Education Foundation, which during 1980 awarded the Council a second grant to support international activities.

Although the bulk of available funds has gone to major projects, there has been a deliberate effort through the years to provide for essential individual contacts and participation in international organizations. On occasion, small travel grants from general funds have gone to foreign librarians to allow them to learn of U.S. developments, and to U.S. librarians to enable them to represent the United States at major foreign conferences. During this fiscal year, grants were provided to Foster Mohrhardt and Rutherford D. Rogers for travel to meetings of the IFLA Programme Management Committee, which they consecutively chaired. Dr. H.D.L. Vervliet, Librarian of the University of Antwerp, received a grant for a study visit to U.S. libraries. Also, the Library of Congress received assistance to allow a representative of the Library to attend the British Lending Library conference on resource sharing held during April, 1981.

INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF LIBRARY ASSOCIATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS

Since the early 1970's, a major channel of CLR support for international library activities has been the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). Ongoing Council grants have supported the work of its secretariat

and the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control. New grants focus primarily on special projects.

Founded in 1927, IFLA has served as a major forum for the discussion of library problems and as a coordinating body for international activities. In 1981, the association listed 990 institutional members, affiliates and library organization members in 111 countries. For a number of years, the organization has held consultative status in UNESCO.

In 1981, the Council granted funding to IFLA to cover travel and related costs for IFLA delegates to visit China to establish an active relationship with the People's Republic, especially in bibliographic matters. Invited by the China Society of Library Science, the IFLA delegates reported that their hosts are interested in becoming involved in international library cooperation.

In early 1979, The Council awarded IFLA a two-year grant for special projects including inquiries into copyrighting bibliographic records and files, conversion of copyrighted materials for use by handicapped readers and conservation of materials.

Copyright and Library Materials for the Handicapped, a study prepared for IFLA by Francoise Hebert and Wanda Noel, was issued in January, 1981. The study examines the special nature

of library services for the handicapped and identifies copyright problems that attend the production and dissemination of materials in special formats, such as Braille. A series of recommendations for IFLA action concludes the analysis. Since 1981 is the International Year of Disabled Persons, the IFLA study comes at a particularly appropriate time to publicize the findings and implement the recommendations.

Related to its interest in copyrighting special materials are IFLA's inquiries into copyright of machine-readable bibliographic records. Major concerns are the conditions of exchange between national bibliographic agencies, the commercial for distributing records received from other sources. Findings from IFLA studies in this area have considerable utility for other CLR programs and projects, especially those within the purview of the Bibliographic Service Development Program.

IFLA has contracted with King Research, Inc. to conduct a study to clarify the issues involved in international exchange of bibliographic records and to propose alternative solutions to some of the problems. The study is expected to produce useful information on the present conditions of exchange of bibliographic records between national bibliographic agencies and their policies on distribution to other agencies.

IFLA INTERNATIONAL OFFICE FOR UNIVERSAL BIBLIOGRAPHIC CONTROL

International cataloging agreements have been a major focus of IFLA effort for a number of years. In 1971, CLR awarded funds for the work of the IFLA Cataloging Committee Secretariat which in 1973 presented a long-term program for developing a worldwide system for the exchange of bibliographic information based on the concept of Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC). In 1974, IFLA transformed the Secretariat into the International Office for UBC and secured UNESCO approval of the concept as a major policy objective. Ever since that time, CLR has supported the work of the office in tandem with national libraries and bibliographic organizations. Additional revenue comes from the sale of publications, contracts and consulting fees. The CLR grant expired in June, 1981.

The concept of universal bibliographic control is an essential element in international thinking about standardization and exchange of information. Both IFLA and UNESCO are working to develop a worldwide system for control and exchange of bibliographic information. Their goals are to make universally and promptly available in an internationally acceptable format bibliographic information on publications issued in all countries. This suggests the construction of an international bibliographic network. There are two assumptions underlying this program: that individual countries are best able to identify and

record their own national bibliographic information, and that acceptance of international bibliographic standards will provide a means of controlling production and exchange of records.

INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL ON ARCHIVES (ICA)

Ongoing grants made possible by the Exxon Education Foundation support supplemented and extended funding for ICA projects during fiscal 1981. The theme of ICA activity has been the worldwide preservation and use of archival sources with special attention to third world countries and newly independent nations. Three projects planned for the year were completed and another funded for implementation in 1981. With funds advanced during 1980, ICA held a symposium at Rio de Janeiro in August, 1980, that dealt with the topic of advancing the status and professional development of archivists and records managers in Latin America, and in a related development, three separate model curricula for in-service training of archival personnel were completed. Designed for use in English, French, and Spanish speaking countries, the curricula were finished in early 1981.

A records management manual designed especially for use in recently independent countries was published during 1980. Thomas W. Wadlow's Disposition of Government Records contains specifications and recommendations for the particular requirements of records management in third world regions. In June, 1981, CLR made a further grant to ICA to test the manual

at a regional seminar on the disposition of government records to be held in New Delhi, October 12-16, 1981. A small grant was also made for the preparation of a manual on the management of archival institutions for use in newly independent nations.

TRAINING AND STANDARDIZATION

Much of the Council's activity on the international scene has involved standardization and extension of library practices and procedures. In line with that interest, a small grant was made to the Forest Press, Albany, N.Y., publisher of the Dewey Decimal Classification, to provide partial support for direct costs associated with investigating the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey classification.

Funds were also provided to the Lesotho Library Association to hold a five-day workshop involving librarians, library school faculty and school administrators. The workshop focused on drawing up a curriculum for professional education for school librarians. The proposed curriculum will be incorporated into teacher training programs in Lesotho.

PUBLICATIONS RESULTING FROM CLR-SUPPORTED PROGRAMS
AND FELLOWSHIPS, 1980-1981

Part I. Programs: General Publications

Gwinn, Nancy E. "CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program: A Symposium." Journal of Academic Librarianship 6 (September, 1980) 196-207.

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Bibliographic Service Development Program

Anable, Richard. "An Investigation of the Holdings Statement Requirements Within a Location System." Prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. November, 1980.

Battelle-Columbus Laboratories, Inc. User Guide for BIBLINK: A Model for Assessing Linking's Economic Impact on the Bibliographic Utilities. Columbus, Ohio, 1980.

Council on Library Resources, Inc. Bibliographic Service Development Program. Bibliographic Service Development Program Report, 1978-1980. 1981.

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Dodd, Sue A. "Cataloging Machine-Readable Data Files: An Interpretative Manual." Chapel Hill, North Carolina, November, 1980.

Harris, Howard, and Patricia Harris. "Requirements and Design Considerations for a Standard Means of Library Identification." Prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. September, 1980.

Jones, C. Lee. Linking Bibliographic Data Bases: A Discussion of the Battelle Technical Report. Washington, D.C., 1980. ED195 274.

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Mandel, Carol, and Judith Herschman. "Subject Access in the On-line Catalog." Prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. April, 1981.

OCLC, Inc. Development Division. Technical Report on Development of Non-Roman Alphabet Capability for Library Processes. Report no. OCLC/DD/TR80-9. August, 1980.

OCLC, Inc., and the Research Libraries Group, Inc. Online Public Access to Library Bibliographic Data Bases: Developments, Issues and Priorities. Washington, D.C., 1980. ED195 275.

Smalley, D.A., et.al. Linking the Bibliographic Utilities: Benefits and Costs. Columbus, Ohio, Battelle-Columbus Laboratories, 1980. ED195 276.

Task Force on a Name Authority File Service. Requirements Statement for the Name Authority File Service. Washington, D.C., 1981.

College Library Program

Hardesty, Larry, and Frances Gatz. "Application of Instructional Development to Mediated Library Instruction." Drexel Library Quarterly 16 (January, 1980) 3-26. (DePauw University)

Lee, Joann H. and Arthur H. Miller, Jr. "Introducing Online Data Base Searching in the Small Academic Library: A Model for Service Without Charge to Undergraduates." Journal of Academic Librarianship 7 (March, 1981) 14-22. (Lake Forest College)

Lubans, John. "Library Literacy." RQ 19 (Summer, 1980) 325-328. (University of Colorado)

Materials and Methods for Sociology Research. New York, Libraryworks, 1980. (University of Wisconsin-Parkside)

Piele, Linda J., John C. Tyson, and Michael B. Sheffey.
Materials and Methods for Business Research.
New York, Libraryworks, 1980. (University of Wisconsin-Parkside)

Salem State College. Department of Interdisciplinary Studies.
Project ASC. Community Resources Directory. A Guide to Local and Regional Resources Including Museums, Historic Sites, and Special Libraries Pertinent to the Teaching and Learning Experiences Within the Humanities.
Salem, Massachusetts, June 30, 1980.

Project and Program Reports

American Library Association. Office for Library Personnel Resources. The Racial, Ethnic and Sexual Composition of Library Staff in Academic and Public Libraries. Chicago, 1981.

Arntzen, Etta and Robert Rainwater. Guide to the Literature of Art History. Chicago, American Library Association, and London, The Art Book Co., 1980.

The Changing Role of Public Libraries. Background Papers From the White House Conference. Compiled by Whitney North Seymour, Jr. Metuchen, N.J., Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1980.

Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity. Interim Report on Book Paper. Washington, D.C., 1981.

Crouch, Dora, Pat Molholt, and Toni Peterson. Indexing in Art and Architecture: An Investigation and Analysis. 1981.

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International Conference on Cataloguing Principles, Paris, October 9-18, 1961. Report. Edited by A.H. Chaplin and Dorothy Anderson. London, IFLA Office for UBC, 1981.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. An Annotated Bibliography of the International Standard Bibliographic Description. 2d ed., rev. Occasional Papers, no. 6. London, IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.

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. ISBD(PM): International Standard Bibliographic Description for Printed Music. London, IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.

. International Access to MARC Records: A Summary Report With Recommended Text for a Bilateral Agreement for the International Exchange of MARC Records. London, IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.

. Supplement to Names of Persons: National Usages for Entry in Catalogues. 3rd ed. London, IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.

Kirkendall, Carolyn A. "Library Use Education: Current Practices and Trends." Library Trends 29 (Summer, 1980) 29-37.

Stevens, Norman D., ed. Essays from the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar. Metuchen, N.J., Scarecrow Press, 1980.

U.S. Library of Congress. Preservation Office. A National Preservation Program. Proceedings of the Planning Conference. Washington, D.C., 1980.

Wadlow, Thomas W. Disposition of Government Records. N.p., 1980.

II. Fellowships

Childress, Boyd. "East Tennessee University Library: The Civil War and Reconstruction Years." Tennessee Librarian 32 (Winter, 1980) 40-46. (CLR Fellow, 1979-1980)

Creth, Sheila D. "Manpower Planning, Job Analysis and Job Evaluation." November, 1980. (CLR Fellow, 1979-1980)

Halporn, Barbara. "Libraries and Printers in the Fifteenth Century." Journal of Library History 16 (Winter, 1981) 134-142. (Advanced Study Fellow, 1976-1977)

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
 CLR-SUPPORTED PROJECTS ACTIVE IN FISCAL 1981 (unaudited)

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

FY 1981

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities Washington, D.C. AAAH/ARL sponsored meeting of research librarians and scholars	-0-	\$ 1,500	\$ 1,000	\$ 500
American Library Association Chicago, Ill. Ethnic and sexual compo- sition/salary survey for librarians	\$ 6,928	-0-	6,928	-0-
Collection management institute	-0-	5,150	4,000	1,150
Financing online search services	-0-	7,110	5,000	2,110
Associated Colleges of the Midwest, Chicago, Ill. Manual to guide study of collection use in small academic libraries	26,553	2,100 (3,383)	25,270	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C. Academic Library Program	203,500	-0-	60,000	143,500
Collection assessment for small academic libraries	-0-	11,200	-0-	11,200
ARL/RLG joint project on decision support systems for libraries	-0-	30,000	15,000	15,000
Association for Asian Studies, Inc., Ann Arbor, Mich. South Asia Library Workshop	-0-	4,500	4,000	500
Boston Theological Institute Cambridge, Mass. Two-year serial cataloging project	2,582	-0-	2,582	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Council of National Library and Information Associations Haverford, Pa. Continued support of the American National Standards Committee Z-39	\$ 15,000	-0-	\$ 15,000	-0-
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind. Periodical list for <u>Choice</u>	2,200	-0-	-0-	2,200
5th Conference on Biblio- graphic Instruction	-0-	5,900 (473)	5,900 (473)	-0-
Forest Press, Albany, N.Y. Investigation of the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification	-0-	6,000	-0-	6,000
International Council on Archives Paris, France Special projects	15,000	3,464	15,464	3,000
Additional projects	-0-	20,000	-0-	20,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Insti- tutions, The Hague, Netherlands Professional activities of the secretariat	30,000	-0-	30,000	-0-
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control	31,756	-0-	28,000	3,756
Special projects	64,000	-0-	22,000	42,000
Costs to establish IFLA/ P.R.C. liaison	-0-	5,000	4,000	1,000
Lesotho Library Association Lesotho, Africa Workshop for training school librarians	-0-	5,500	5,000	500

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Library of Congress Washington, D.C. Fifth Assembly of State Librarians	-0-	\$(1,678)	\$(1,678)	-0-
Travel grant for L.C. representative at British conference on resource sharing	-0-	1,000	-0-	\$ 1,000
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication program	-0-	11,000	11,000	-0-
MIDLNET, Chicago, Ill. Toward salary of a technical advisor	17,778	(19,278)	(1,500)	-0-
Foster Mohrhardt, Arlington, Va. Travel grant to chair IFLA Program Management Committee	4,688	(4,575)	113	-0-
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advance- ment of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga. Status report on libraries of black public colleges	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C. College Library Program	-0-	(933)	(933)	-0-
Plainedge Public Library Massapequa, N.Y. Research to determine reasons for nonuse of public libraries	9,750	-0-	-0-	9,750
C.W. Post Center of Long Island University, Greenvale, N.Y. Faculty development project in information science	-0-	10,000	9,000	1,000
Rutherford D. Rogers New Haven, Conn. Travel grant to chair IFLA Program Management Committee	-0-	6,000	2,800 (669)	3,869
Society of American Archivists, Chicago, Ill. Pilot project for self-study and peer review of archives	18,670	-0-	9,000	9,670

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
University of California, Berkeley, Calif. National shelflist measurement project	\$ 8,293	-0-	-0-	\$ 8,293
University of California, Los Angeles, Calif. Third edition of <u>Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries</u>	9,500	-0-	-0-	9,500
University of Kentucky, Lexington, Ken. Preparation of "Leaders in American Academic Librar- ianship 1925-75"	6,000	-0-	2,000	4,000
University of Wyoming, Laramie, Wyo. <u>Support of Conservation Administration News</u>	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000
Wright State University Dayton, Ohio Internships for masters degree students in archival and historical administration	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
Subtotals	477,698	135,424 (30,320)	285,557 (5,253)	302,498

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	FY 1981			
	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Academic Library Management Intern Program				
1978-79	590	(40)	550	-0-
1979-80	5,810	(2,119)	3,691	-0-
1980-81	111,639	-0-	85,740	25,899
	<u>118,039</u>	<u>(2,159)</u>	<u>89,981</u>	<u>25,899</u>
Bibliographic Service Development Program				
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Ill.				
LAWNET planning meeting	2,500	(216)	2,284	-0-
Richard Anable, Binghamton, N.Y.				
Preparation of a position paper on holdings statements	-0-	2,600 (59)	2,541	-0-
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D.C.				
ARL microforms project	-0-	20,000	-0-	20,000
Battelle Memorial Institute- Columbus Laboratories Columbus, Ohio				
Study of linking of biblio- graphic utilities	62,208	-0-	62,208	-0-
Training in the use of the BIBLINK model	-0-	15,068	4,009	11,059
Augmentation of the BIBLINK model and preparation of a users guide	-0-	16,500	16,500	-0-
Dartmouth College Library Hanover, N.H.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs Phase 2	-0-	12,919	-0-	12,919

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Howard Harris & Patricia Harris Silver Spring, Md. Position paper on an institution identi- fication code standard	2,000	-0-	1,334	666
Institute for Research in Social Science, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, N.C. Machine-readable data files cataloging manual	1,998	-0-	1,750	248
Library of Congress, Washington, D. C. Conversion of retrospective name authority files	165,000	-0-	102,000	63,000
Travel costs re. the linked authority system project 1980 (with RLG & WLN)	17,000	(9,791)	7,948 (739)	-0-
Travel costs re. the linked authority system project 1981 (with RLG & WLN)	-0-	21,000	828	20,172
Travel grant for U.S. representative at Copenhagen meeting on an international authority system	1,105	(32)	1,073	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs - Phase 2	-0-	16,351	5,000	11,351
Carol Mandel, Judith Herschman & Laura Kassebaum Subject Access Paper	-0-	2,500	2,500	-0-
J. Matthews & Associates Grass Valley, Calif. Participant in joint project to define standard data elements & data collection methods for online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	9,500	7,375	2,125
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs - Phase 2	-0-	99,500	-0-	99,500

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
Northwestern University Evanston, Ill.				
Development of an application level protocol	-0-	36,000	-0-	36,000
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs Phase 2	-0-	25,260	-0-	25,260
OCLC, Dublin, Ohio				
Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (joint project with RLG)	2,150	-0-	2,150	-0-
Participant in joint pro- ject to define standard data elements & data col- lection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	25,000	22,500	2,500
Pittsburgh Regional Library Center, Pittsburgh, Penn.				
Serials cancellation project	-0-	24,000	-0-	24,000
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Troy, N.Y.				
Planning a thesaurus for the fields of art & architecture	10,000	-0-	6,944	3,056
The Research Libraries Group, Inc., Stanford, Calif.				
Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (Joint project with OCLC)	2,150	(12)	2,138	-0-
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN & LC) Phase 1	126,488	-0-	126,488	-0-
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN & LC) Phase 2	-0-	165,542	41,386	124,156
Inclusion of three research libraries in preliminary work for online public access catalog project	-0-	19,892	18,000	1,892

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid (6/30/81)
Research Libraries Group, Inc. Stanford, Calif.				
Joint project to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	26,850	24,000	2,850
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs - Phase 2	-0-	116,614	-0-	116,614
James E. Rush Associates, Powell, Ohio				
Preparation of a paper on the role of regional networks	-0-	10,425 (22)	10,403	-0-
Norman B. Stevens, Storrs, Conn.				
Preparation of a paper on the role of regional networks	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Stanford University Libraries Stanford, Calif.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs - Phase 2	-0-	20,960	-0-	20,960
University of California, Berkeley, Calif.				
Participant in joint pro- ject to define standard data elements and data collection methods in online public access catalog evaluation	-0-	5,650	5,100	550
Participant in joint pro- ject to evaluate online public access catalogs - Phase 2	-0-	22,000	-0-	22,000
Analysis of data collected in the online catalog evaluation project - Phase 3	-0-	113,000	-0-	113,000

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
University of Illinois, Urbana, Ill. Statistical analysis of MARC database.	23,463	-0-	7,893	15,570
Washington Library Network, Olympia, Wash. Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) Phase I	112,250	-0-	20,000	92,250
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG & LC) Phase 2	-0-	182,197	-0-	182,197
Total Bibliographic Service Development Program	528,312	1,012,328 (10,132)	507,352 (739)	1,023,895
Fellowship Program	13,710	(4,510)	3,380	5,820
Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program 1979-80	11,632	(6,145)	6,537 (1,050)	-0-
1980-81	-0-	86,500	81,678	4,822
Library Service Enhancement Program Hampton Institute Hampton, Va.	1,742	(1,011)	731	-0-
Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL) Medical Library Association, Chicago, Ill. Study group in education for health sciences librarianship	-0-	2,000 (559)	1,441	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/80	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/81
University of California, Los Angeles, Calif.				
Senior Fellows Program	-0-	125,000	-0-	125,000
Frontiers Conference	-0-	90,000	-0-	90,000
University of Chicago, Chicago, Ill.				
Special program of advanced study in library management	-0-	250,000	15,000	235,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Basic professional education for research librarianship	<u>-0-</u>	<u>275,000</u>	<u>2,000</u>	<u>273,000</u>
Total PETREL	-0-	742,000 (559)	18,441	723,000
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Travel assistance				
H.D.L. Vervliet, University of Antwerp, Belgium				
Study trip to U. S. research libraries	-0-	2,500	500	2,000
<hr/>				
Total CLR Projects	673,435	1,843,328 (24,516)	708,600 (1,789)	1,785,436
Subtotals page 4	477,698	<u>135,424</u> (30,320)	<u>285,557</u> (5,253)	<u>302,498</u>
TOTALS	1,151,133	1,978,752 (54,836)	994,157 (7,042)	2,087,934